

22RPT03 MultiFixRad

D5 – Report on the realisation of the radiometric high-temperature scale using multiple fixed points, the associated uncertainties and the characteristics of each participants' scheme. The target uncertainties for the implementation of the scale are less than 0.6 °C at 1500 °C and 1 °C at 2000 °C.

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Glossary

Eutectic – Here a mixture of metal and carbon in a ratio so that the melting point is minimised.

FP - Fixed-point, graphite crucible filled with metal/metal-carbon that has a fixed melting/freezing temperature.

NMI – National Metrology Institute

DI – Designated institute

POI - Point of Inflection. the point where a melting curve changes from slowing down to speeding up

SSE – Size of Source Effect

ITS-90 - International temperature scale of 1990

MeP-K - Mise-en-pratique, or best practice, for the realisation of the kelvin

CCT - The consultative committee for thermometry, which advises the CGPM on issues related to temperature measurement and scale dissemination

Fixed-points and shielding gas

Al – Aluminium, 660.323 °C

Ag – Silver, 961.78 °C

Au – Gold, 1064.18 °C

Cu – Copper, 1084.62 °C

Fe-C – Iron-carbon, 1154 °C

Co-C – Cobalt-carbon, 1324.24 °C

Pd-C – Palladium-Carbon, 1492 °C

Pt-C – Platinum-Carbon, 1738.28 °C

Re-C – Rhenium-Carbon, 2474.69 °C

Ar – Argon

NMIs and DIs

RISE – Sweden, Research institutes of Sweden AB

JV – Norway, Justervesenet

LNE – France, Laboratoire national de métrologie et d'essais

CNAM – France, Conservatoire national des arts et métiers

SMU – Slovakia, Slovenský Metrologický Ústav

CMI – Czechia, Český Metrologický Institut

UL – Slovenia, Univerza v Ljubljani

TUBITAK – Türkiye, Türkiye Bilimsel ve Teknolojik Arastirma Kurumu

DFM – Denmark, Dansk Fundamental Metrologi A/S

DTU – Denmark, Danmarks Tekniske Universitet

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1 Summary

This document summarises the kelvin dissemination schemes developed at each of the less experienced NMIs in the project, as well as Tübitak. The document contains a brief overview of the current status for relative primary thermometry with high temperature fixed points (HTFPs) and radiation thermometers as the interpolating device. It then proceeds with details on the cells constructed by the laboratories, the equipment used when the cells are realised as calibration points, and discusses how the cell quality has been assessed and the uncertainty attributed to the cell realisations in each laboratory.

In the end an assessment of the interpolation uncertainty is presented. It depends strongly on the selection of fixed points, the ability of each laboratory to carefully evaluate the radiation thermometer characteristics, and the realisation uncertainties in each case. It is seen that for some of the laboratories involved it can be better to use a subset of the created cells, partly due to the cell quality, and partly due to the present ability to realise the cells with sufficient precision. While this assessment may be seen as recommendations for each laboratory, it should be noted that with improved experiments the recommendations may change in the future. Further improvements are possible in most of the laboratories.

This document will be modified and submitted to a journal for peer review.

2 Introduction

The redefinition of the kelvin in 2019 was the culmination of years of systematic work undertaken by the largest NMIs, partly in order to determine the Boltzmann constant with the precision required for the redefinition, and partly to prepare for a new dissemination environment. In particular, primary methods whereby the temperature is deduced from a system property (electrical noise, radiation, acoustic resonances or other) which can be theoretically related to temperature from first principles, is expected to gradually becoming real alternatives [1] to the scale measurement according to ITS-90 [2]. For high temperatures, fixed point-based radiation thermometry is seen as an imminent candidate for a practical realisation of the kelvin above around 1000 °C [3]. One reason for that is the practical similarity with the ITS-90, which many laboratories already implement in the relevant temperature range.

While radiation thermometry may also be used to as an absolute primary method without any reference to known temperatures [4, 5, 6], this requires a direct traceability to other SI quantities, usually to primary radiometric standards but also conceivably to electrical standards [7], and also a meticulous characterisation of the pyrometer used. This complicates the experiments significantly. The use of a limited number of fixed points as references may simplify the experiments substantially: for instance in the current ITS-90, while the spectral response of the pyrometer must still be known, the only radiometric reference needed is one of the fixed points Ag, Au or Cu. If one could use two fixed points, the effective wavelength of the pyrometer can be fitted to the observations [8, 9], and with three or more one does not need a detailed knowledge of the spectral response. In both cases one can exploit the fact that the commonly used Sakuma-Hattori equation,

$$S(T) = a_1 \frac{1}{\exp\left(\frac{c_2}{a_2 T + a_3}\right) - 1}$$

can be rewritten in terms of the spectral response of the pyrometer by expressing a_2 and a_3 as [10]

$$\begin{aligned} a_2 &= \lambda_0 (1 - 6r^2) \\ a_3 &= \frac{c_2}{2} r^2 \end{aligned}$$

Here λ_0 is the mean wavelength of the spectral response, and $r = \sigma/\lambda_0$ is the relative bandwidth of the response, which must be small. For two calibration points the fitting coefficients are λ_0 and a_1 , while for three or more calibration points a_i are fitted directly. The importance of the relative primary schemes, where one or more temperatures are used to calibrate the pyrometer, is that the interpolation function can essentially be deduced from the Planck law and hence that the interpolation function used may be deduced from basic physics: the errors arising from some minor simplifications are small and negligible if r is small [11]. Moreover, interpolation uncertainty due to uncertainty in the calibration points may be computed with established methods [12]. Fitting the response to calibration points is essentially an indirect way of characterizing the pyrometer, with the caveat that extrapolation beyond the calibration range should be avoided with three or more points and done with care with two points. The relative primary radiation thermometry schemes rely on fixed points with a thermodynamic temperature assigned. The CCT publishes [13] a limited list of high temperature fixed points (HTFP) with assigned temperature and associated uncertainty, which may be used by laboratories to disseminate the kelvin in any range needed.

Extensive work has been undertaken by several NMIs in the past decades to prepare this list, and to investigate the reliability of the selected fixed points. Above the Cu point metal-carbon eutectics are used, to eliminate the otherwise unavoidable contamination of C from the crucibles, the feasibility of which was demonstrated by Yamada et al in 1999 [14]. Since then extensive work has been undertaken to understand the details of the phase transition processes [15, 16, 17], such as the effect of impurities [18], the conditions in the furnace used to realise the phase transition [19, 20, 21, 22], and methods to extract the plateau features from data [23, 24, 25]. The work has now matured to the point that recommendations for uncertainty budgets in HTFPs are

published [26]. With a suitable pyrometer with a low SSE, good stability and good linearity [27, 28], laboratories should be able to establish radiation temperature scales based on HTFPs.

However, so far such scales have only been implemented in NMIs at the highest level. In this work we present recent efforts by 10 European NMIs to establish radiation thermometry scales based on HTFPs. The work was undertaken as part of a European Partnership for Metrology project (23RPT03 MultiFixRad [29]), with contributors from JV (Norway), RISE (Sweden), DFM and DTU (Denmark), CMI (Czech Republic), SMU (Slovakia), UL (Slovenia), and with knowledge transfer from LNE-Cnam (France) and Tübitak (Türkiye). We describe the facilities at each of the laboratories, the outcome of the characterisation work performed, and show how the different laboratories may exploit the flexible nature of the new MeP-K to tailor appropriate calibration schemes for various needs.

3 Fixed points

Figure 1 Sketch of the fixed point cell design used in this work. Not shown are the sleeve surrounding the ingot, and the sheets of C between the sleeve and the crucible wall which serve both as strain relief and thermal homogenisation. The cavity diameter is larger than the aperture.

All the laboratories used the same crucible design, shown in Figure 1. The design has been developed by LNE-Cnam [30] and has proven to be robust to stresses induced by thermal expansion, with a sufficient ingot mass to induce long plateaus in typical furnace environments, and achieve a high emissivity of the cavity at an opening suitable for high-end radiation thermometers, while limiting the physical dimensions to enable control of the temperature gradients across the cell during plateaus. All the cells constructed for this study used graphite parts ordered from the same supplier in the same batch (SGL Carbon, SIGRAFINE R6710). Assuming isothermal inner walls and a wall emissivity of 0.85 the geometry gives an effective cavity emissivity of 0.9997 for a representative radiation thermometer relevant here. The calculation of emissivity, however, is based on the assumption that the graphite surface reflects light diffusely. Machining may partly polish the surface of graphite, leading to a more complicated optical behaviour. However, as discussed by Yamada [21], a lid in front of the blackbody with a smaller aperture than the blackbody diameter will reduce the loss of specularly reflected light from the cavity bottom with a large incidence angle on the sidewall of the cavity. Hence, some of the adverse effects of specular reflection will be alleviated by our cavity design.

Each laboratory filled a collection of cells of their own choice, using the piston method again pioneered by LNE-Cnam [30]. The method reduces the number of melting operations required to typically two, although in a few cases more melts were needed to ensure a homogeneous and complete ingot. The cells constructed by each laboratory are summarised in Table 1. They are all members of the current list of fixed points with assigned thermodynamic transition temperatures published by the CCT [13]. As is clear from the table, the laboratories have chosen different combinations of fixed points, in part determined by the temperature range they need to cover, partly by the availability of pure materials at the time this collaboration was started, partly

by the available instrumentation at the laboratories, and finally by the funding available for materials purchase at the laboratories. We will later discuss the impact of these choices for the scales implemented.

Table 1: Overview of the fixed points constructed by each laboratory, with purity in each case. The purity values are taken from specifications and are typically the guaranteed minimum from the manufacturer.

Fixed point	Purity C fraction by weight (ingot mixture)						
	JV	SMU	CMI	RISE	DFM/ DTU	UL	Tübitak
Ag	99.99 %	99.999 %	-	99.999 %	-	-	-
Au	-	99.999 %	-	-	-	-	-
Cu	99.99 %	99.99 %	99.9999 %	99.99998 %	99.99 %	99.99 %	99.999 %
Fe-C	99.99 %	99.99 %	-	99.99 %	-	99.99 %	99.995 %
	2.8 %	3.6 %		3.5 %		3.4 %	4.2 %
Co-C	99.99 %	99.995 %	99.995 %	99.999 %	99.99 %	99.99 %	99.995 %
	2.5 %	2.0 %		2.1 %		2.0 %	2.3 %
Pd-C	99.99 %	99.99 %	99.99 %	99.99 %	99.99 %	99.99 %	-
	1.7 %	1.7 %		1.7 %		2.9 %	
Re-C	-	-	99.99 %	99.99 %	-	-	99.999 %
							0.9 %

The table also shows the starting fraction of C used for preparing the ingots. Recommended starting fractions can be extracted from the literature, e.g. Fe-C [31], Co-C [32], Pd-C [33, 31], and Re-C [34], but are typically a little below the eutectic composition of the specific alloy. Small deviations from these values would normally not result in issues with the cells. However, the metal would form the eutectic mixture from C in the crucible parts if not enough has been supplied prior to the first melt, potentially weakening the crucible walls and reducing the lifetime of the cell. On the other hand, some of the laboratories also inadvertently started with too much C when trying to make the first Pd-C cell. This resulted in a C rich layer forming, which seemingly blocked flow of the eutectic melt, leading to a large void in the ingot near the blackbody aperture and a mass substantially lower than expected.

The equipment used to realise the fixed points is shown in Table 2. In all cases appropriate arrangements for inert atmosphere were installed, in some cases using pre-installed Ar gas control systems, and in some cases as a retrofitted arrangement. The Thermo-gauge furnace used at CMI and RISE already have Ar protective gas installed, since the work tube/heater element is made from graphite. Precautions to ensure uniform temperature at the location of the fixed points varied. RISE used a 3-zone furnace with fine tuned offsets in the front and back zone to optimise the uniformity in the center zone. To further improve the uniformity, several layers of graphite wool padding, cut and adjusted to fit inside the work tube and to ensure optical access without vignetting, were added at the front and the back of the cell. In the single zone furnaces used by SMU and JV, uniformity was improved by carefully placing layers of insulation behind and in the front of the cells, again ensuring unobstructed optical access for the radiation thermometers. Due to the optical access the heat loss was much larger via the front, resulting in a slightly shifted gradient profile inside the work tube, and the fixed point location was shifted accordingly during the experiments. At RISE the 3-zone furnace was operated with an additional graphite holder that completely encased the fixed point (except for the optical access) and further improved the temperature uniformity. The furnace at UL was a tube furnace with 7 heating zones controlled independently, which enabled very small gradients at the location of the fixed point. The furnace control is based on software developed at UL.

Table 2: Furnaces used by each laboratory to realise the fixed points. The design of the heating zones are listed, and the resulting temperature gradients across the length of the cells, at the optimal position in the furnaces, are shown in each case in the gradient column. The repeatability values are taken from repeated realisations of the cells. They include minor changes in cell position between different runs, as well as some variations resulting from (moderate) changes in ramp rates and set points above the melt.

Lab	Furnace		Heating zone	HTFPs used	Gradient	Repeatability
	Manufacturer	Model				
JV	Carbolite-Gero	TF1 16/60/180	1-zone Tube Alumina	Ag, Cu, Fe-C, Co-C, Pd-C	1.5 K @1650 K	0.1-0.2 K
RISE	Entech	ETF 50/18-III	3-zone Tube Alumina	Ag, Cu, Fe-C, Co-C, Pd-C	± 0.8 K @ 1000 °C	0.2-0.5 K
	Thermo Gauge		1-zone, graphite tube/heater	Fe-C, Co-C, Pd-C, Re-C	± 2 K @ 1000 °C ± 4 K @ 1800 °C	1-2 K
DFM	DFM	DFM	3 zone, alumina tube, MoS2 heating elements	Pd-C, Co-C	Less than 1 K	0.02 K
SMU	Isotech	Oberon R426	Na heatpipe	Ag, Au, Cu	Less than 1 K	0.5 K to 1 K
	Vecstar	THL V1600	1-zone Tube Alumina (dia 50 mm)	Fe-C, Co-C, Pd-C	Less than 1.5 K (in the middle of furnace)	1 K to 2 K
CMI	Isotech	ITL-M-17702(H)	Na heat pipe	Cu	(0.2 - 0.3) K	0.01-0.5 K
	Clasic CZ	5018T-3Z	3 zone	Co-C	Less than 1K alongside the FP	1 K
	Thermogauge		1 zone	Co-C, Pd-C, Re-C		(1 – 2) K
UL	Home made	No model	7-zone Tube Alumina	Cu, Fe-C, Co-C, Pd-C	Less than 1 K	0,5 K

The setpoints used are typically 10-15 K above the melting point for the eutectic points, and 10-15 K below the freeze for the Ag and Cu cells used. During the freeze RISE conducted a systematic study on the Cu cell where both ramp rate, dwell times and setpoints have been varied from their usual settings, with little effect on the freezing temperature determined from the data. Todd et al prescribes that HTFPs should exhibit weak dependence on the setpoint [26], below 70 mK variation for Co-C when changing the setpoint from 10 to 30 K above the melting temperature. We note that this of course also requires a well aligned pyrometer with a low SSE.

The ramp rates have been varied by some of the laboratories (RISE, SMU, UL). The current practice among the laboratories varies, from using slow rates from 3 K/min to fast rates up to 30 K/min. The actual rates of change experienced by the ingot are usually slower, in particular in the cases when the cell has been protected by an additional graphite holder.

4 Pyrometers

Table 3: Overview of the radiation thermometers used in this study. JV and DFM used custom built devices from commercial optical and electronic components. The other laboratories used commercial devices, some of them several years old.

Laboratory	Instrument		Spectral data, μm		Spot size, mm	SSE	NL
	Manufacturer	Model	Peak	Width			
JV	JV Detector: Hamamatsu	C10439-03	0.94	0.0055	1	Indirect method, up to 20 mm	Detector: <XXX
DFM	DFM Detector: Basler camera	BFS-U3	0.80051	0.011	1	Direct method	Checked
RISE	KE Technology	LP5	0,65	0.013	1	Indirect method up to 30 mm	
SMU	CHINO	IR-RST65H	0.65105	0.004851	1	Direct method, up to 22 mm	Checked
CMI	KE Technology	LP5	0.6492	0.00435	1	Indirect method, up to 35 mm	-
UL	Sensortherm	DS09	0,9	0,4	1,1	Direct up to 36 mm	
Tübitak	KE Technology Tübitak	LP5 TSP-2	650.57 907.26	3.96 9.96	1	Indirect up to 100 mm	<0.0002

The pyrometer instrumentation used is summarised in Table 3. RISE, SMU, Tübitak and CMI use commercial devices which are widely recognised among NMIs as high quality devices with low SSE, excellent linearity and stable operation over time. Tübitak, SMU and CMI have measured the relative spectral response of their instruments and the spectral characteristics in the table are measured values (including uncertainty). The values for the device at RISE are taken from the manufacturer specifications. While we do not include full SSE curves here, the table contains example values for specific diameters.

Figure 2: Outline of the optical setup for JV's radiometer. DFM's radiometer is similar, but with the camera as a detector as well as viewfinder. The Lyot stop is positioned in the plane where the collimation lens images the objective lens, to block unwanted scattering from the rim of the objective. The diameter is a little smaller than the image to block as much light as possible. This also means that the Lyot stop defines the effective diameter of the entrance. The optical components are separated in different compartments to avoid stray light on the detector (not shown on the sketch).

DFM and JV constructed devices from commercial optical components. JV based the design on the designs by [28, 27]. An outline of the optical path is shown in Figure 2. Not shown in the figure is a beamchopper placed before the collimation lens. It was introduced because the detector is not temperature controlled, and it was necessary to monitor the dark current continuously during experiments. The detector is a Hamamatsu model with an integrated pre-amplifier to output a voltage signal from 0 to 10 V, nominally. The range actually used is much smaller, at approximately 0.4 V at the Pd-C point. The voltage is read using a Keysight DAQ970A data acquisition station, which is also used to acquire readings from two thermistors located close to the interference filter and Lyot stop, and to supply the operational voltage to the detector package. A more detailed description of the device will become available elsewhere. However, a few important observations are relevant here. Firstly, the objective lens used is a Thorlabs achromat doublet, AC508-150-B-ML. Yoon et al [27] found that Thorlabs lenses were not optimised for low SSE. This is probably one of the reasons that the SSE performance of the device is poorer than that found by Yoon et al and Lowe, or compared with previously published curves such as in [21, 20]. The JV device has been carefully aligned and precautions taken to reduce stray light inside the optical system, but it is still possible with further optimisation. Secondly, there are some internal apertures in the system that do not have an optical function but are needed to hold e.g. the thermistors used to measure (and control) the temperature of the interference filter and the Lyot stop. It is possible that this leads to some more stray light being transmitted to the detector. In order to manage this better it is necessary to tailor some of the mechanical parts.

In any case, the performance has been found to be satisfactory for the establishment of the scale. The device has been used to measure the melting plateau in Pd-C point at both JV and RISE: the realisations were performed with different cells, different furnaces and different melt conditions, with less than 30 mK difference in the value. Further work will be carried out in the near future to improve the SSE management of the device.

DFM originally based the design on the same work as JV but used a camera as the detector. The camera has been carefully characterized with respect to its integration time and chip uniformity as well as nonlinearity. The integration time is adjusted to ensure good pixel filling without saturation, and this is done by optimizing the integration time to ensure around 80 % pixel saturation at the fixed point plateau. The camera used is a Basler ace with a Sony IMX273 CMOS sensor ensuring 12 bit readout. This limits the signal resolution to the bit step but pixel averaging and time averaging ensures that this enters the uncertainty budget to a small degree.

The use of a camera enables direct imaging of the fixpoint or other sources ensuring easy alignment, as well as quick automated mapping of source uniformity. This is very powerful for quick characterization of blackbody as well as oven uniformity.

The camera and bandwidth filters are temperature controlled at fixed temperatures within 20 mK. As for the JV device the optimised designs by Yoon et al and Lowe are the basis, and the device contains several apertures, carefully positioned, to limit stray light, and the internal lenses and the field stop aperture are chosen such that a Ø3 mm target will just be visible in the camera image. The SSE is limited by the use of Thorlabs lenses resulting in an imaging spotsize around 1.5 mm and will be replaced.

5 Results and discussion

Table 4: Melting range, slope at the POI and the assigned realisation uncertainty of each cell. The melting ranges and slope are values taken from best cases in each laboratory, after optimisation of the setup. The realisation uncertainties are discussed in the text but excludes components that may be attributed to the radiation thermometer. It should be noted that some contributions to uncertainty are effects that arise in an interplay between the radiation thermometer and the fixed point, so the categorisation of contributions is not always clear.

Lab	Fixed point	Melting range, mK	POI slope, $\mu\text{K/s}$	Realisation U, k=2, K
JV	Ag	n/a	n/a	0,42
	Cu	n/a	n/a	0,26
	Fe-C	170	9,1	0,27
	Co-C	4000	4247,7	0,36
	Pd-C	60	39,4	0,46
SMU	Ag	n/a	n/a	0,44
	Au	n/a	n/a	0,32
	Cu	n/a	n/a	0,31
	Fe-C	954,5	2448	0,42
	Co-C	4224,8	6814	0,42
	Pd-C	588,7	2030	0,44
RISE	Ag	n/a	n/a	0,21
	Cu	n/a	n/a	0,19
	Fe-C	580	1783	0,38
	Co-C	180	183	0,31
	Pd-C	450	1517	0,45
CMI	Cu	n/a	n/a	0,11
	Co-C	80 - 170	107	0,43
	Pd-C	n/a	n/a	0,85
	Re-C	n/a	n/a	2,24
DTU	Co-C	6994	n/a	n/a
DFM	Pd-C	258	n/a	0,6
UL	Cu	n/a		
	Fe-C	140		
	Co-C	190		
	Pd-C	550		
Tübitak	Cu			0,08
	Fe-C			0,18
	Co-C			0,22
	Re-C			0,86

Table 4 contains a summary of three possible performance measures for the melt process in each fixed point. The table includes Ag, Au and Cu for reference: the appropriate calibration point is the freezing point in those cases. Here we are mainly concerned with the results for the eutectic points.

The melting range is an important quality indicator for HTFPs. It is a measure of intrinsic cell qualities such as the metal purity and the size of voids in the ingot: low impurity and high filling fraction are associated with low melting ranges [26]. Other effects associated with the realisation of the melt, such as temperature gradients across the cell, misalignment of the radiation thermometer, or the position of the cell inside the furnace, may

cause wider melting ranges, and hence a high melting range is in itself not a sign of an intrinsically bad cell. However, provided the range is below limits used as selection criteria when the thermodynamic temperatures of HTFPs were determined [26, 16] one can usually assume the cell and realisation is of sufficiently high quality to be used as calibration reference. For the method used here to determine the range, those limits are approximately 0.12 K (Co-C) and 0.30 K (Pt-C).

In the table, most of the eutectic fixed points fulfil the recommendations. However, there are some exceptions. The Co-C cells made by JV and SMU far exceed the recommended limits. The values stated are the best achieved at both laboratories, after several attempts where the furnace environment was checked and attempted optimised, and the radiation thermometer was meticulously aligned. It is clear that the cells used are unsuitable for calibration purposes. During filling, the cells had more or less the expected amount of Co from the volume of the crucible and the density of Co. It seems unlikely that the issue is voids in the ingot. On the other hand, both cells appear to indicate a suppression of the melting point by around 3-4 K compared with the assigned temperature in the MeP-K [13]. This could indicate impurities, although the depression of the transition temperature is unexpectedly large. While the suppression effect to some extent depends on the species, Bloembergen et al [18] found that for Co purity similar to the one we have used here, the suppression of the liquidus point is on the order of 0.2 K. One possibility is that the manufacturer purity claim is wrong, possibly to the extent that the dilute limit used by Bloembergen et al is no longer valid. It is also possible that, because of the steep slope during melt, determination of the melting temperature is very hard to do.

The table also contains a column for the realisation uncertainty. The contributions taken into account here are limited to effects pertaining to intrinsic cell properties and the furnace environment the cells are realised in: impurities, furnace effect, furnace gradients, repeatability of the plateaus, POI identification, the temperature drop, and the structure effect. The temperature drop is calculated based on the prescriptions in the MeP-K, using the dimensions of our cells and a standard emissivity for graphite (0.86) as inputs. The impurities contribution is taken from standardised normal case values in a report from working group 5 in the CCT [35], and the structure effect contribution is taken from standardised (normal case) values in [26] and only used for Fe-C and Co-C. The POI identification contribution is assigned in slightly different ways and depends on how the POI is determined. Here, a repeatability contribution from multiple realisations of each cell implicitly includes this contribution. The uncertainty in POI identification includes the contribution from signal noise, which typically is small.

The attribution of values for the furnace effect is more difficult. Previous work has studied the effect by realising the same cell in different furnaces. Bourson [19] tested Co-C, Pt-C and Re-C in two different furnaces under the assumption that the furnace effect can be explained by the temperature gradients. A later experimental study on the same cells by Dong et al [20] used three different furnaces, optimised the fixedpoint realisations in all three, and tried to account for all known effects, among them the temperature gradient. A residual, unexplained furnace dependence was observed and the authors concluded with a recommendation that the standard uncertainty ($k=1$) be increased by 80 mK (Co-C) and 240 mK (Re-C) in the absence of further knowledge. However, Yamada [21] proposed that the mechanism of the furnace effect is an anisotropic reflectance of graphite whereby for large incidence angles light is reflected specularly with high reflectivity. The effect is to increase the radiative heat transfer from the cavity bottom through the furnace opening to the ambient temperature. In line with this mechanism, an aperture in front of the blackbody cavity was found to reduce the furnace effect. This finding suggests that the cell design used here to some degree alleviates the furnace effect. The values used in the uncertainty budgets are based on those recommended by Dong et al, scaled appropriately with temperature from 50 mK at Ag to 90 mK at Pd-C, but in light of the previous argument these may be conservative estimates.

We follow the implication from the work by Yamada that an enhanced, furnace dependent heat transfer to ambient is the root cause of the effect and separate from the effect of furnace gradients. On the other hand, the gradients in a furnace are of course depending on the furnace geometry, the heating elements, and the insulation surrounding the cell: in essence, furnace specific features, and these effects must also be represented in the uncertainty budget. Bourson [19] found that an optimal position exists in any furnace, where the temperature at front and back of the crucible are similar, and that the apparent melting temperature is reduced when the cell is moved away from the optimal position and the front and back temperature difference increases. The effect was found to be larger at higher temperature, roughly 50 mK at the Pt-C point with a

10 K temperature difference from front to back. The measured gradients in the furnaces used here are summarised in Table 2. We have attributed a standard uncertainty from 10 mK (Ag) to 50 mK (Pd-C) here.

The thermal inertia of the furnace and any protective elements surrounding the fixed point may affect the point of inflection and, to a lesser extent, the liquidus point [24]. This may also be attributed to a furnace effect. In our case we have not explicitly considered this effect, but the laboratories have carried out systematic experiments where the setpoints and ramp rates have been varied. The variation is absorbed in the reproducibility contributions.

The Table 2 contains an estimate of the reproducibility for each laboratory and cell. But this is a somewhat ill-defined concept with fixed point cells, as they should represent stable and reproducible references. Todd et al [26] acknowledges that there are still some unknown contributions, either because some known effects are underestimated, or because as yet unidentified effects are present. But because this is not fully understood, one cannot rule out that there are unidentified peculiarities at each laboratory which affects the melt realisations. The table column contains the outcome of repeated plateau realisations, some of which include variations in the setpoints and ramp rates. In many cases the scatter represents the most important contribution to the realisation uncertainty.

Todd *et al* [26] point out that using the POI requires that the cell has been realised under similar conditions and with similar construction as those used to determine the POI in the mep-K. This is because the POI does not represent a physical state of the system, it is merely a convenient feature in a typical (good quality) melting curve that can be reliably and repeatably identified. The POI can be influenced by several confounding effects, such as misalignment of the radiation thermometer. On the other hand, the two common methods for determining the liquidus point relies on a determination of the POI first: the extrapolation method takes the tangent to the melting curve at the POI and extrapolates to the end of the melt, while the fraction method uses the curvature of the melting curve prior to the POI (more details are available in e.g. [36]).

Figure 3: Plot of realisation uncertainties at the different laboratories. The typical values from Todd et al are shown for reference.

Figure 3 summarises the realisation uncertainties in Table 4. Also shown are values taken from the normal case in Todd et al [26], disregarding the contribution from emissivity and the contribution from T assignment in order to directly compare the values.

Figure 4 Various possible schemes for JV, given the realisation uncertainties and disregarding the contributions from the pyrometer. One-point schemes: issue at JV is the lack of proper spectral data, which renders Cu and Pd-C too low. Fe-C and Pd-C gives the best overall results in the range. No examples are shown which includes the Co-C point because of its poor quality: see the main text.

Figure 5 Possible schemes at CMI, given the realisation uncertainties of the fixed point cells. Many possibilities have been omitted from the display for clarity: they are cases where the extrapolation leads to large errors in parts of the range. Using all 4 calibration points are shown as a reference in the black curve. Since CMI has good spectral data on their pyrometer, using an ITS-90 scheme is possible, shown as the two blue curves. For the other cases the relatively large uncertainty in the Re-C point dominates the fits, in many cases even at lower temperatures.

Figure 6: Possible schemes at SMU. As for JV, the Co-C cell is excluded due to its poor quality. The lines assumes the uncertainty in the realisations listed in Table [] is used: again, this does not take into account some of the radiometer-specific uncertainty contributions. The solid black line is the expected uncertainty for the SMU radiometer if all the cells are used. (contrast with CMI). Typically, within the relevant temperature range, There are no major differences between the schemes shown in the figure, except for Au, Cu and Pd-C used together.

Figure 7: Possible schemes at RISE. RISE constructed a Re-C cell as well, but the quality was found to be insufficient for use. The remaining cells available to cover the range up to 2500 °C are all calibration points in the lower end and significant extrapolation is necessary. The red lines show n=2 schemes, and the blue lines n=1 schemes. See text for an extended discussion.

Figure 8: A selection of possible schemes at Tübitak, with their custom built device TSP-2. Since the pyrometer can be characterised in detail, it is possible to use the extrapolation scheme with $n=1$: using Cu as the reference, this provides the lowest uncertainty in almost the entire range. At low temperatures there is some benefit in utilizing more than one fixed point. It is an advantage to use more evenly spaced points if e.g. three points are used.

A useful feature of the Mep-K in its revised form is that there is a rich flexibility in the choice of which fixed points to use. In the following we will illustrate this point by inspecting the results of the laboratories in more detail. As will be clear, the combination of realisation uncertainties and the ability to bring further information about the radiation thermometer has an impact on the optimal choice, with sometimes surprising outcomes. The analysis also points towards ways to improve the calibration uncertainties. Based on the realisation uncertainties we can compute interpolation uncertainty in the various schemes, for instance using the software developed in the project [36]. The results are shown in Figure 4 to Figure 7. In each case we have used the wavelength of the radiometers taken from Table 3. In addition, the uncertainty attributed to the eutectic points by the CCT is taken into account.

For JV (Figure 4), the fact that the spectral response of the system (detector + interference filter) has not been measured, the $n=1$ scheme should not be used. The manufacturer specifications for the spectral filter are also recorded at a lower temperature than used at JV (controlled at approximately 28.5 °C, a few degrees above ambient). However, it could be noted that using the $n=3$ scheme the fitted coefficients give a $\lambda_0=0.939 \mu\text{m}$ and $\sigma=0.004 \mu\text{m}$. The issue with the $n=3$ scheme for JV is that extrapolation is necessary from the Pd-C point up to 1800 °C. Figure 4 clearly shows how the uncertainty will become impractically large at that temperature. Even without the contributions from the radiation thermometer and emissivity of the cavities it is already 1 °C at 1800 °C ($k=1$). Instead, the two-point scheme using Fe-C and Pd-C gives a reasonable extrapolation behaviour outside the calibration range, while enabling the shifted peak wavelength to be fitted to the data rather than measured independently. Using Ag or Cu in addition to Pd-C gives similar results, however if Pd-C is omitted the extrapolation results in too large uncertainty at 1800 °C. The examples for $n=3$ and $n=4$ are similar. Without an additional calibration point closer to the upper limit both cases give large errors there.

For CMI (Figure 5), whose aim is to establish a reference up to 2500 °C, the best choice is in fact to extrapolate from the Cu point. There are two reasons for this. Firstly, CMI has the facilities to measure the spectral response of their pyrometer with high precision, which means the $n=1$ scheme is a viable choice. The second is that currently, the realisation uncertainty at the Re-C point dominates in most of the schemes that involve that point. For a more restricted temperature range, e.g. between Cu and Co-C, the two-point scheme is competitive, but extrapolation to the upper part of the range leads to very large uncertainty (not shown in the figure). Even using all four fixed points leads to a larger uncertainty at the high end of the range, again because the Re-C point dominates.

The examples for SMU (Figure 6) contrasts with the CMI results. Part of the reason is that CMI has reasonably small uncertainties at all the fixed points. SMU also has high-precision data on the spectral response of their pyrometer, and the $n=1$ scheme is a viable alternative. In the relevant temperature range (1000 °C to 1600 °C) the figure shows expected uncertainty for the Au and Pd-C points: choosing Ag, Cu or Fe-C gives similar results. However, in this case the $n=2$ scheme is a competitive option provided the Pd-C point is one of the two.

RISE has plans to implement a Re-C cell, but so far the melting range is unacceptably high. The suspected cause is insufficient purity, similar to the Co-C cells of JV and SMU. The aim of RISE is to cover a temperature range up to 2500 °C, possibly extending to 3000 °C. As a result, the $n>3$ schemes cannot be used with the present selection of working cells, as is clearly seen in Figure 7. With appropriate cell selections, the extrapolation methods ($n=1$ and $n=2$) give acceptable precision even at the high temperatures. At temperatures below 1500 °C the $n>3$ schemes provide a similar precision, but no obvious advantage over the extrapolation methods shown. Until RISE has a functioning Re-C cell it seems the best choice remains either to use extrapolation from the Cu point, or a two-point scheme with Pd-C as one of the cells. An issue with the $n=1$ scheme at RISE is that the pyrometer spectral response relies on the manufacturer specifications.

6 Lessons learned, discussions, conclusions

For the present work, the laboratories faced significant challenges in obtaining metals of the required purity. This may be an issue in the future without a simple solution. For much of the previous work carried out in preparation for the determination of the thermodynamic temperature of the eutectic melts, 5N or even 6N material was used. In addition, the process for cell selection described in [16] assumed that the dominant effect of impurities would be to lower the transition temperature and hence that cells with a higher transition temperature were better (purer material). However, for the present work, we could usually only identify sources of 4N. Since the supplier specifications are typically phrased as a minimum purity, we may well find that we have used higher purity materials in reality. This may also be one explanation for the discrepant Co-C results. SMU and JV used the same batch of Co when building these cells, with a 4N purity according to the supplier. The Re-C cell constructed by RISE was similarly using 4N purity. It is possible that the sample meets the specifications in both cases, but only just. This could be an explanation for the lower-than-expected melting temperature and the large melting range observed.

The large contribution from reproducibility of the cells is a surprising result if the experiments are carefully executed. A number of the usual uncertainty contributions can be ruled out as explanations: the impurities, geometry, emissivity and furnace properties are not expected to change between runs. On the other hand, there are many effects that could change slightly between experiments, such as the placement of the cells inside the furnace, the alignment of the pyrometer used, the consistency of the determination of the POI, the structure effect (to the extent that freeze conditions matter), and possibly the location of any voids in the solid ingot. One other issue is that the graphite surfaces may change after heat treatment: JV has observed some discolouring of the Pd-C cell after repeated experiments. If this affects the wall emissivity it might affect the temperature drop and the effective emissivity of the cavity. However, the largest contributor is most likely the pyrometer itself. For the scale realisation this is important to keep in mind to avoid accounting for the same effect twice. In practice, the calibration of the pyrometer is performed by one or two realisations of each fixed point, with repeated melt realisations each time. The average measured signal at the POI would be used in the calibration: this average includes the repeatability of both devices (the cell and the pyrometer). When the pyrometer is later used in calibrations one would of course need to take its stability into account again.

The scales established at the laboratories have not been compared directly here. While the uncertainty in each laboratory (from Section 5) could be used as a metric for comparison, the different scales must be compared directly before one can draw any conclusions about quality and precision. This is done in an on-going Euramet comparison, the Euramet-T.K10, and the results will be available in due time. The measurements are scheduled to complete before the end of 2026.

7 Bibliography

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